

The Role And Articulation Of Islamic Politics As An Effort Of Spiritualization Of A State After The Sole Principle Of Pancasila

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Abstract

Indonesia is not a religious but nor a secular country. As a country that is based on Pancasila, Indonesian Muslims are slowly but surely given role color in development, especially the development in the field of religion. New phenomenon already showed a significant tendency in the case of the relationship of Muslims and the State, especially in the field of social and political life. Various interests of Muslims people who are increasingly accommodated by the government. At the beginning of the New Order, the Muslim political activists get fresh air as their "elan vital" recover to its full been active on the national political stage. Enthusiasm and optimism this is what makes sense suppose because they do have a very significant contribution in the Old Order regime toppled along ABRI and students, through their organizations. Things far more important than that is how Islam in substantiate articulation context of its teachings provide a wider meaning and enjoyment by the people of Indonesia in pluralistic by the ideologue, Muslim activists, political thinkers intelektualis and until Islam really appear as rahmatanlil 'âlamîn.

Introduction

Before the passage of the Ormas and Orsospol Law with the sole principle of Pancasila, a tension of government and Muslims often occur. The disharmony of relationship between the government and Muslims is caused by various things. One of them is considered to be a political sentiment from the Center of Strategic and International Studies (CSIS) led by Ali Murtopo that Islam can be a threat to the survival of the Republic of Indonesia. The role of CSIS, according to Azyumardi Azra, is clear, namely formulating policies, citing the Nurcholish Madjid which was delivered in a seminar in Leiden, Netherlands in 1996, about Christianization programs in Indonesia. From the beginning of the New Order, the regime was anti-Islamic, especially when under the control of Ali Murtopo, including Soedjono Hoemardani who always encouraging the growth of anti-Islamic forces, such as the survival of kejawen or kebatinan to appear to reduce the role and influence of Islam, when it also runs a depoliticization program or even political de-Islamization, which according to Azyumardi, reached its zenith when Soeharto was supported by Ali Murtopo who succeeded in fusing Islamic parties and the sole principle of Pancasila.

For the activists of new Islamic movement, this is seen as a new challenge within the political articulation framework of Muslims. To maximize their role, various strategies were adopted, for example, the renewal of Islamic thought through ijtihad which is trying to approach the authorities by offering a development role, including the social and political role of Muslims by entering the bureaucracy formally, and turning NGOs and mass organizations as the informal way by revealing an accommodating attitude towards the ideology of the sole principle of Pancasila. Indonesian Muslims, according to Nurcholish Madjid, can approve the Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution based on at least two considerations; first, its values are justified by the Islam dogma; secondly, its function is as the proofs of agreement between various groups to realize political unity. This view confirms that the position of Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution can be accommodated as long as it does not conflict with Islam, on the contrary, Islamic values can be accepted as enrichment of meaning and value as long as it does not conflict with Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution. This jargon is clearly ahistorical and a distortion of facts which is very dangerous for the interpretation of Indonesian political development.

The sole principle of Pancasila for community organizations (mass organizations), including religious organizations and socio-political organizations (orsospol) is the most important milestone in the New Order era (1967-1998), because after the acceptance of Pancasila as a sole principle, the government obtains constitutional legitimacy to continue the development in all fields. How the forms of articulation of the political struggle of Indonesian Muslims during the New Order era, especially after the acceptance of Pancasila as the sole principle by Muslims, became significant to be studied more deeply. Nurcholish Madjid said that Muslims do not need to be confronted with Pancasila, because Pancasila is a common ideology, which from the point of Indonesian Muslims - as the basic view of Islamic figures such as Teuku Moh. Hasan. A. Wahid Hasyim, Ki Bagus

Hadikusumo, Kasman Singodimedjo, etc. - who are the principles that serve as a meeting point and equality between Indonesian Muslim citizens and non-Muslim citizens to support the Republic of Indonesia.

The articulation of Indonesian Islamic thought in the early 1970s was marked by the emergence of an Islamic thought movement which was inspired by Nurckholish Madjid which came to be called a "kelompok permbaharu" driven by changes in political, social and economic realities that were born in the New Order era. Probably, this new fact, by Abdul Munir Mul Khan, is referred to as the interaction process of understanding religion with the cultural and social political environment. Likewise, Islamic thought is experiencing dynamism due to the economic and political pressures which are experienced by a new intellectual Islamic generation. Islamic study is continuously developed through scientific study in campuses, dialogues to religion on television, and writings that are shared to the public, in order to contribute to how to overcome various difficulties that are being faced by people. Thus, Fachry Ali said that the new political tradition is not uncommon for a religious community, so it has an empirical and historical and socio-cultural foundation that is stronger and rooted in Indonesian society.

Responding to the phenomenon of the New Order which has succeeded in resolving the historical trauma that has arisen in the competition to create religious community ties vis a vis nationality, into the state hegemony ties. According to Tobroni and Syamsul Arifin's analysis, it is required to prioritize religious issues (Islam) to obtain structural legitimacy, unlikely to be maximally successful. Therefore, there must be a follow-up in the form of creative endeavors, namely by participating in development process. Muslims get blessing in disguise in the form of increasing enthusiastic religious activities which he calls the rise of cultural Islam after the enactment of the sole principle of Pancasila. Religious passion can be seen from the lively taklim assemblies and recitations and Islamic da'wah to the government and private offices.

Pancasila as a political ideology

The word ideology comes from the word idea, which is one of the most important teachings of Plato (428/427 -348 BC), the son of Arsiton and Perictione, since he was young, he interested in the teachings of democracy Pericles and Socrates. Idea is the basis for everything. The idea masters the realities that exist, both in the world that is born and the unseen. Therefore, knowing the world of ideas is very important and fundamental. According to Plato, idea is the goal of true knowledge. The idea of the place is in another world. All knowledge is a copy of the original, which manifests itself through the memory of the origin soul. The soul acts as a mediator between the world of ideas and the material world. Through the eyes, the soul is reminded of what it already knows before descending into the material world. Therefore, vision serves as a link which function to recall the knowledge of the soul. This is the essence of Plato's epistemology.

Ideology becomes a very strategic term because it is synchronized with politics, which is important to understand in order to explain and predict the politics and problems of power. Ideology does not have a single meaning, because it has multiple interpretations in the realm of social science. In general, it can be said as a doctrine that guides political action, ideals that must be believed to be political "faith", goals that must be achieved, reasons to be fought for, and visions of the best society that must be realized. For this reason, ideology teaches members of the political movement all matters relating to policies that must be pursued, determining who friends and opponents. Psychologically, in addition to providing confidence and stability, every political ideology always propagates and transmits anxiety viruses to its adherents which in turn thickens the sense of threat and hostility.

The feeling of threat and hostility, signified by Ian Adams, if the political ideology or political will is at odds with one's religious understanding, causing tensions that are difficult to avoid. For example, between the political will, the government sets a single ideology of Pancasila for mass organizations and orsospol clearly seen to cause a new tension, because the reaction of rejection from various organizations through speeches and demonstrations is quite widespread. Fear and tense envelop the political atmosphere. Politically, sociologically, and psychologically need time to address and decide whether it can accommodate the government's desire for the interests of stability and dynamics of development, in this context, it should be considered. The solutions offered by Tobroni and Syamsul Arifin, namely by making approaches persuasively and dialogue intellectuals on an ongoing basis, especially by the government by empowering the mouthpieces of intellectuals, as it was done by Nurcholish Madjid through the HMI he leads.

Ian Adams emphasized that the main point of ideology is about values, namely how to act with others and live together in a society. All ideologies have a conception of an ideal society which will also uphold the values held by that society's ideology. Then formulate programs to bring reality closer to the ideal, therefore, ideology has a certain understanding of the human condition and offers theories of human nature that are far-reaching and ideal of society, presenting a more or less coherent vision of human reality. Government programs, that are responsive to the problems faced by the Ummah, seem to have melted the attitude against activists of Islamic political thought, persuasive approach by accommodating the interests of the Ummah, as it was explained clearly by Abdul Aziz Thaba below; the Drafting of the Religious Courts Bill, the Muslim Charity Foundation

for Pancasila, the Muamalat Bank, the Islamic Mass Media, the birth of ICMI, the freedom of *da'wah* pulpit and so forth.

Pancasila as the basis of the state, although through tough debate, can be accepted by Muslims, the formulation of Pancasila - a word adopted from Sanskrit - fits well with Muslims, because the main problem is that the state is built in accordance with Islamic teachings, both in theory and in practice. The basis of the state can be formulated in general clauses as long as they reflect the will of Islam. Pancasila is an open ideology, therefore an ideology that does not have a single meaning which means to have multiple interpretations can be filled with cultural values and religious values, especially Islam which is a religion that has a majority in Indonesia. From this gap, Muslim political activists take part through social movements, social movements.

Social movement is a serious effort by a group of people in a large society (the state) and they are professional to change the main points of the nation's culture into a new culture which is considered more beneficial to the life of the nation in the future. Even though the majority of Indonesians claim to be Muslim, Hidayat Nataatmadja said, only a small handful of people truly had the motivation to take part in various movements that raised the banner of Islam. Therefore, the existence of figures who become the driving force is very important in a movement. In this context, social movements or reform movements that want to combine Islamic values into the ideology of Pancasila as a new culture, namely the Pancasila culture, as the principle of national and state life, need to be fully supported by Muslims by providing their political participation and taking good order and decline bad order.

However how the Pancasila ideology concept is good or not, but if it is associated with Albert Einstein's screams cited by Mohammad Hatta, then it should be cautious and vigilant to hidden political interests, a great thinker based on political empiricism also complains if it is not a priori towards politics with said:

"...This cannot be denied that the conflict of economic interests within each nation and between nations has led to dangerous and threatening conditions in today's world. People do not succeed in developing forms of political and economic organization, which will ensure that the nations of the world live side by side in peace. People have not been able to build a system that can eliminate the possibility of war and permanently eradicate those dangerous tools to mass destruction."

The important point of the above quotation seems to justify the empirical phenomenon before the eyes of people of Indonesia, who recognize and approve the sole principle of Pancasila, a state ideology that is ideal for a pluralist Indonesian nation. However, the economic factors that crush the Indonesian people seem to be the main factors causing the emergence of obstacles, challenges, disruptions and threats to national development. Political organizations also trigger cross political disputes, both in the KPU, double Election, Legislative Elections to the Presidential and Vice President Elections. This shows that it is not the Pancasila factor that is wrong, but the man behind the gun, greedy humans, uncontrolled political lust, greed on property have triggered officials to commit criminal acts of corruption.

In the era of reforms there have been political turmoil, political upheaval, rampant corruption, the emergence of tax mafias, legal mafias, century bank cases, Hambalang cases, scarcity of fuel, electricity, basic food and so on, then appearing in *Senayan* in an effort to make the Ormas Bill, perhaps because the sole principle has been deemed a failure. Buya Syafi'i Ma'arif, in this case, suggested that fundamental political change must be constitutional. Changes outside of that, he added, were feared would cause anarchy and ask for victims. So it is appropriate that the review of the Pancasila single principle through the Mass Organization Bill as discussed in *Senayan* this political year.

State Spiritualization

The role and political articulation of the Muslim community after the adoption of Pancasila as the sole principle for ormas and orsospol was presented by the community gathered in reform groups who provided interpretations of Islamic teachings (*sharia*) to be implemented in the life of the nation and state under the umbrella of Pancasila. The significance of renewal here, due to the existence of *ijma'* and also new changes and developments which are *sunnatullah* in nature, form, and phenomena both in material and social life and thought, then the mistaken assumption that the door of *ijtihad* has been closed has created a contradiction between the perfection of religion and renewal in the religious sciences. L Stoddard just loudly said that *ijtihad* continues to be opened especially for those who qualify as a *mujtahid*, carry out reforms in order to maintain the teachings of Islam that never left behind which always excels in every place and age.

In the context of reform, Mohammad Hatta said that Indonesian intelligence has a moral responsibility for the development of society. Whether he sits in the leadership of the state and society or not, he will not be separated from that responsibility. Although they are not a leader, as a people-democrat he must rebuke and oppose the wrong doing by showing improvements according to his beliefs. For Hatta, the most important thing is that humanity must become a way of life and hold the struggle to achieve truth, justice, goodness, happiness, prosperity, peace, independence and brotherhood over this mortal world. Hatta's affirmation was an expression of his responsibility as an activist in the Islamic movement with the concept of *al-amr bi al-ma'rûf wa an-nahiy an al-munkar*.

Related to intelligence or intelligence of a person with politics, it is interesting to show here an analysis of Ahmad W. Pratik, that between intelligence and politics are not two contradictory things, but neither they are two things that can be unified. It can be illustrated in the model of the world political transaction scheme and the world of scholarship as follows:

Group (A) is the practical political area, while the group (AB) is the area where a scholar can perform political functions without leaving the world (clothes) of his intelligence. In (AB), a scholar is a moral force (which together with other social forces) can fulfill political functions, among others, can throw ideas renewal, convey the aspirations of the community or carry out social control over the political life that has taken place. Where when a scholar has migrated leaving (B) and (AB) to (A) means he no longer wears the attributes of scholars. However, he may still has scholarly behavior, although for the full extent when he was still in the group (B) or (AB), it is rather difficult, because in some cases, the behavior of practical politicians (especially in Indonesia) with intellectual behavior cannot be integrated, incompatible. From this schema, it can be seen that a scholar, or intelligence as a motor of the movement to spiritualize the State, as long as he has not been contaminated with political lust, ambitious in power, then he can still be followed in line with his struggle.

Spiritualization of the state is a necessity because the values of Islamic teachings are not counterproductive to Pancasila, in this case, the enrichment of Islamic values in the implementation of Pancasila as the basis of national and state life is an attempt of Muslim intellectuals and activists of new political Islamic thought to uphold the universal Islamic values in the country. Nurcholish Madjid argues as an effort to give substance to national values and their development, culturally and sociologically is inevitable, because Muslims are the largest community living in this country. Nevertheless, the Islamic values that will be developed should be universalized as a consequence of a pluralist state, at least in the expression "Truly Islam always reveals that Islam is for the universe, for the good of all people", *rahmatan lil 'hmmm*. So it is not only by and for Muslims, but also the values of goodness for all the people of Indonesia and even the world.

Bahtiar Effendy in his research book stressed that the government's accommodation of various Muslim interests is realized through government policies that are considered positive by Muslims. The policies are broad spectrum and structural, legislative, infrastructure and cultural. It seems that through these government policies, Muslims can take a wider role in the interests of the people, nation and state in accordance with the methods of struggle that originate from the Qur'an and Sunnah. One of the basic values of Islamic teachings (sayari'ah Islam) in the nation and state is the implementation of social justice in life. The basic view of Pancasila in the context of the state of life principles of justice is mentioned in the framework of "just and civilized humanity" and "social justice". This fact, according to Nurcholish Madjid, it shows the high ideals of justice in the concept of statehood, even clearly stated that "social justice for all people" is the goal of the state.

The struggle for the state's spiritualisation for Muslims is clear, namely realizing Indonesia as an ideal state by implementing the principles or values of state life, as pointed out by Masykuri Abdillah that the ideal state according to Islam, namely the State that applies the ideal principles as follows: honesty and accountable (al-amânah), justice (al-'adâlah), brotherhood (al-ukhuwwah), respect for pluralism (al-ta'addudiyah), equality (al-musâwât) consultation (al-syûrâ), prioritizing peace or pluralism (al-ta'addudiyah), equality (al-musâwât) consultative (al-syûrâ), prioritizing peace or pluralism (al-ta'addudiyah), equality (al-musâwât) consultative (al-syûrâ), prioritizing peace or pluralism (al-ta'addudiyah) (al-silm), social control (al-amr bi al-ma'r'f wa an-nahy 'an al-munkar), as well as implementing Islamic sharia as a law applicable in the State. Actually there is no problem in the context of statehood under the principle of Pancasila, because there is not the least bit of hope in the framework of controversial state spiritualisation. So the state can accommodate the wishes of Muslims to implement spiritual values in life.

Muhammad Imarah indicated that justice was an implementation of the universal moderate attitude of Islam. On this basis, for Islam, Pancasila is not a problem. Because the elements of justice and truth are gathered in it which creates a fair attitude between the two poles of extremism which mediate it. Between Muhammad Imarah and Mohammad Hatta are seen to be equally consistent with the command to implement Islamic teachings (justice, truth, goodness, peace, equality and so on) in the life of the nation and state in society, regardless of any form of government of a country. In this case, the Indonesian people are based on Pancasila, which is indeed formulated by the contribution of the thoughts of Muslim activists who are undoubtedly their credibility and integrity.

Articulation Forms of Political Struggle

The New Islamic Generation after the adoption of Pancasila as the sole principle for mass organizations and social organizations continues to fight Islamic politics in various forms.

1. Intellectual movement

Articulation of intellectual movement, in this case, appears a new intellectualism among Indonesian educated Muslim thinkers and intelligentsia; generally, there are three important themes in the discourse of this new Islamic intellectualism, namely:

a). Re-form the theological foundation of political Islam.

Based on previous experience, it is very difficult to dialogue Islam and the state in order to find common ground of the vision and mission of each party, this is an obstacle to the development of a harmonious synthesis between Islam and the state, because Indonesian society is a society that is sociologically and culturally diverse, then the relationship formalistic or legalistic between Islam and the state cannot be accepted by all parties. By not changing the belief that Islam has a holistic character, however, the new Islamic thinkers and organizer assess that it does not require mixing between the sacred (Islamic values) and profane ones (the state, political organizations, ideologies, orsospol, etc.)

Budhy Munawar-Rachman said that translating theology in the framework of overcoming the situation of social crises (of course including political crises) caused by a development strategy that had put the elite and a small number of people as the beneficiary class, while the majority of the people as the disadvantaged class, became a necessity urgent. Then theology must have social relevance as a "movement" which ultimately takes the interests of the majority of the people. According to Budhy, this movement is called a transformative Islamic theology movement. Among them, theologically, people must not despair, must carry out social criticism, uphold social justice in society, and so on,

b). Redefining Islamic social political ideals

Islamic social political ideals must already refer to a collective agreement, namely Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution. As it is known that the New Order has succeeded in changing the nature of political debate to be "pragmatic". After successfully fusing Islamic parties into PPP, in 1985, it means that the New Order has closed the Islamic struggle meeting to formalize Islam in the state constitution, *because Indonesia has imposed a sole ideology, Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution. The efforts to redefine the social and political aspirations of Islam are only focused on two main themes; first, the development of egalitarian and democratic political arrangements; second, the development of processes towards economic equality. if there is an unharmonious relationship between Islam and the State it will have an impact on the marginalization of the political role of Islam, or at the very least, the loss of opportunities and opportunities for Islamic political activists to participate fully in the political processes in Indonesia.

M. Amien Rais asserted that building an egalitarian society is by implementing Islamic teachings in the country, whose leaders are oriented towards social welfare and always eliminating, at least minimizing human exploitation of other humans in all their forms and manifestations. Amien's opinion is of course not oversimplified, but it seems that he clearly emphasizes that the government / Indonesian authorities must truly uphold democracy and respect the existence of small people, because without people there is no government and no state, remember that.

Nurcholis Madjid, in the context of building this egalitarian society, citing Ernest Gellner who pointed to two characteristics that make Islam relevant in modern times, namely the egalitarian and scientific nature, then he said that from the prioritization of the egalitarian ethos (which places the emphasis on the principle of democracy and social justice) and scientific ethos (which places the emphasis on the principles of openness and the relativity of truth in humans and in flowing times). Islam develops and continues to develop through the development of *ijtihad*, critical and moderate attitudes, in addition to the participation of all walks of life on the basis of equal rights and obligations.

c). Revisiting Islamic political strategy

Citing Lukman Harun's opinion, Bahtiar effendi began his discussion about the inevitability of reviewing Islamic political strategy, because:

"In the past, Islamic parties were often considered to represent Muslims, so the aspirations of the people were often identified with those party's aspirations, even though this was actually not the case, because only a portion of Muslims entered the Islamic-based party. However, after the three socio-political organizations (PPP, Golkar and PDI) were based on Pancasila, there was no longer an official Islamic party that carried the voice of Islam. The aspirations of Muslims are now in various political and social groups "

Lukman Harun's statement above is an expression of the political response of one of the Islamic political activists to the implementation of the single principle of Pancasila for ormas and orsospol. Because the political reality shows that, the political strategy of Islam should be reviewed. In the past, political Islam

was the monopoly of the activities of Islamic parties, now Muslims who are not in line with Islamic parties are described as secular or hypocritical. Therefore, Islamic political strategy is aimed at the non-integrative or partisan style which includes the first, the affirmation of Islam as the state ideology and the second, urging the legalization of the Jakarta Charter.

This explanation of Bahtiar is echoed by a group of contemporary Muslim reform activists who are pro-shari'a, namely the political Islamic movement that fights for the enforcement of Islamic sharia in state life. The concrete form of the struggle is an appeal to return to the Jakarta Charter - a constitutional document containing the basis of the Pancasila State with its first formulation of the principle of "Godhead with the obligation to carry out Islamic shari'ah for its adherents. - This movement is echoed and spearheaded by Islamic organizations. For example, the Indonesian Committee for Islamic World Solidarity (KISDI), the Indonesian Mujahidin Council (MMI), the Indonesian Hizbut Tharir (HTI) Islamic Defenders Front (FPI) and the Ahlussunnah Wal Jama'ah Communication Forum, known as the Lasykar Jihad.

2. Participation in bureaucracy and politics

Articulation in the form of participation in bureaucracy and politics, was started by a generation of Muslims engaged in new forms of intellectualism or Islamic thought reform movements. Under the patronage of the "technocratic groups" around Widjono Nitisastro and Sumitro Djojohadikusumo, the senior of Islamic generation chose to participate in the government, they were the technocrats who at that time controlled the bureaucracy.

The important factors that have been explained above seem important to be understood in depth so that the relationship between Islam and the government becomes more harmonious, because of the mutual accommodation of each other's interests. The government, for example, issued a variety of policies that have broad meaning for the interests of Muslims as a whole. Various policies that can be called among other things, the ratification of the Act. Education No. 2/1989. The Religious Courts Law, and the Joint Decree on the Utilization of Zakat, the wearing of the veil in schools, the establishment of the Pancasila Muslim Charity Foundation, and Bank Mu'amalat; Revocation of the SIUPP tabloid Million in order to send 1000 da'i to transmigrant areas; the formation of ICMI, the recruitment of Islamic leaders into the DPR / MPR, the large number of Muslims being appointed Minister of Development Cabinet, and the availability of the President and Vice President to open various religious events, such as conferences of Islamic institutions.

Nevertheless, the Islamic ummah also shows an accommodating attitude towards the government. Muslims, for example, began to leave their reactive and emotional attitudes and replace them with participatory attitudes - rational. Political aspirations of Muslims in general elections began to vary. In Aceh, for example, Golkar won the 1987 and 1992 elections. In fact, Aceh has always been known as the PPP's groups among ulama' who also supported Suharto's leadership, for example by proposing that he remain President of the Republic of Indonesia from 1993-1998. In addition, Harto's relationship with the scholars also showed improvement, for example, it can be seen when the halal bihalal celebration was held after Eid al-Fitr at the Palace in 1994.

Abdul Azis Thaba indicated that discussing politics in Indonesia could not be separated from the Muslims, because it was Muslims who were the majority of the population of Indonesia. Therefore, sociologically, the potential of Muslims as a source of legitimacy of the political system in the framework of the success of national development is enormous, in every election, the image of Islam is always displayed. Gradually, the relationship between Islam and the state has become increasingly accommodating since the mid 1980s until now. To build an illustration of the improved relations between Islam and the state, here is Abdul Azis Thaba's perception diagram:

Gradual figure of islam and state relationship

After reading the diagram, it shows that the relationship between Islam and the State experienced ups and downs, even disharmony, since the beginning of the New Order, especially when Ali Murtopo who, at

that time, led CSIS, as mentioned earlier, made a discriminatory policy line against Islam, even Azyumardi Azra alleged that there was de-Islamization. Then from 1982 to 1985, tensions between Islam and the State began to soften, especially since the government's desire to uniform the principles of mass organizations and orsospol under the umbrella of Pancasila. Islam and the state have mutual understanding and mutual need, but there is still mutual suspicion between the two. However, since 1985 there has been a harmonization of relations, due to the accommodation of each party. The state in this case the government is well aware that political legitimacy through elections is very important, and the majority of the population is Muslim, so that the maximum political participation of Muslims will be accommodated in the interests of Muslims, and vice versa, Muslims are no longer suspicious of government political will.

3. Empowerment of grassroots communities

Articulation in the form of empowering the lower classes (grassroots) through the social transformation movement. The background is that there is a basic assumption that the objective conditions of the Indonesian Muslim community are socio-economically weak, so that their social and political support and participation in the dynamics of New Order development is very small. For this participation to be greater, the majority of the lower class (wong cilik), their economic, social and political potential needs to be empowered. The social transformation movement which seems to be a diversification of the meaning of Islamic politics was pioneered, among others, by those working in various Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs). The area of cultivation of this group revolves around issues of poverty, health, ignorance, underdevelopment, unemployment, social, economic and political injustice.

In order to reflect more deeply on efforts to play the role and political articulation of Muslim intellectuals in the future, especially to reformulate the political strategy in the bureaucracy and government, it is better to follow the thesis of Indonesian development acceleration based on the special characteristics of the Indonesian people in the layers of Indonesia grassroots as a concept reference, which has been formulated by Fuad Amsyari, namely:

- a. The majority of Indonesian people are Muslims who are associated with Islamic characteristics both in terms of philosophy, worship, morality and culture.
- b. The Indonesian people in general are still patrimonial social patterns which means respecting and imitating parents, teachers, superiors, leaders or rulers in many attitudes of their daily lives.
- c. The Indonesian nation is relatively new to escape from the traumatic conditions of colonialism, because the authorities at that time were antipathy towards Islamic values, exploitative and authoritarian behavior.
- d. The very long colonial process that was able to result in changes in the genetic structure of the nation in the form tended to have an inlander mentality that was easily discouraged, yes man, as long as it survived, and was not creative because it was accustomed to getting instructions from superiors. On the other hand, the occupation also had an impact on the imitative behavior of some of the population on colonialist behavior, such as being arbitrary, feeling righteous of themselves, deceiving and blackmailing others, and phobias towards the teachings of Islam if they had the opportunity to rule.

This Fuad Amsyari formula can be a constructive reference for political Islam reform experts and activists in Indonesia, as a basis for psychological understanding, so that the role and political articulation of Muslims in the national and state insights can be maximized. What has become an obsession to empower lower class people to participate in national and state life, both improving the quality of performance, the quality of business, the quality of political participation, the quality of life and the quality of faith must be enforced through the exemplary elite of the nation's leaders according to the way of life, morality, including worship in the framework of increasing piety to the Creator, as well as maintaining Indonesian culture. In governmental system, it should not be authoritarian, but rather prioritizes deliberation to reach consensus, moreover to show arrogant attitude and colonize its own people. However, this should show more attitude to protect, protect and fight for their fate in all lines of political policy of his government.

Closing

The Islamic Thought Reform Movement associated with political thought in Indonesia is a form of honest and creative intellectual response to the socio-political development that was widely accommodated by the ruling government at that time, when the Declaration of Pancasila was the sole principle for mass organizations and orsospol, the New Order regime under the leadership of Muhammad Soeharto. The existence of Islamic reform movement seems to have shown the role of intellectuals in building cohesiveness amid a "conceptual tension" between New Order politics and the aspirations of Muslims. The implications of social life, economy, politics and even bureaucracy are very clear nuances of Islam, there are no more arrests of Muslim activists, and the preachers (ustadz) are increasingly enjoying "pulpit freedom", even religious assemblies are increasingly lively, how the dynamics of Islam culture are growing since the 1980s.

- 1- Some important things that might be considered as evidence that the relationship between Islam and the bureaucracy is increasingly conducive to national development, including; 1). Articulation in the form of

intellectual movement, 2). Articulation in the form of participation in bureaucracy and politics, and 3). Articulation in the form of empowering the lower classes (grassroots) through the social transformation movement. All of them run in a symbiotic manner and give birth to a harmonious relationship between the government and Muslims. As long as the political awareness of Muslims is not "ridden" by practical political interests, there is basically synergic political communication carried out by Islamic scholars and political activists on the perspective of sustainable development for the nation and the state that has constitutional cohesiveness, although this is not based on excite Islam.

References:

- Abdillah, Masykuri, "Negara Ideal Menurut Islam dan Implementasinya pada Masa Kini", dalam, Komaruddin Hidayat dan Ahmad Gaus AF (ed.), *Islam Negara & Civil Society Gerakan dan Pemikiran Islam Kontemporer*, Jakarta : Paramadina, 2005.
- Adams, Ian, "Pengantar Penerbit", *Ideologi Politik Mutakhir, Konsep, Ragam, Kritik, dan Masa Depan*, terj. Ali Noerzaman, Yogyakarta : Qalam, 2004.
- Ali, Fachry, *Golongan Agama dan Etika Kekuasaan Keharusan Demokratisasi dalam Islam Indonesia*, Surabaya : Risalah Gusti, 1996.
- Amsyari, Fuad, *Masa Depan Umat Islam, Peluang dan Tantangan*, Bandung : Penerbit Al-Bayan Kelompok Penerbit Mizan, 1993.
- Amsyari, Fuad, *Masa Depan Umat Islam, Peluang dan Tantangan*, Bandung : Penerbit Al-Bayan Kelompok Penerbit Mizan, 1993.
- Anggaran Dasar HMI dan Penjelasan Asas HMI dalam *Hasil-hasil Ketetapan Kongres ke-16 HMI di Padang 24 sampai 31 Maret 1986*, Jakarta : Penerbit PB HMI, 1986.
- Anwar, M. Syafi'i, *Pemikiran dan Aksi Islam Indonesia Sebuah Kajian Politik Tentang Cendekiawan Muslim Orde Baru*, Jakarta : Yayasan Paramadina, 1995.
- Azra, Azyumardi *Islam Substantif Agar Umat Tidak Menjadi Buih*, (ed.) Idris Thoaha, Bandung : Penerbit Mizan, 2000.
- Carvallo, Bosco dan Dasrizal, (Penyunting.), *Aspirasi Umat Islam Indonesia*, Jakarta : Lembaga Penunjang Pembangunan Nasional (Leppenpas), 1983.
- Effendi, Bahtiar, "Islam dan Negara Transformasi Pemikiran dan Praktek Politik Islam di Indonesia", *P r i s m a*, No. 5, Mei 1995.
- Effendi, Bahtiar, *Islam dan Negara Transformasi Pemikiran dan Praktek Politik Islam di Indonesia*, Jakarta : Penerbit Paramadina, 1998.
- Feith, Herbert, dan Lance Castle (ed.), *Pemikiran Politik Indonesia 1945-1965*, Jakarta : LP3ES, 1998.
- Hatta, Mohammad, *Alam Pikiran Yunani*, Jakarta : Tintamas, 1986, Cet. Ke- 3.
- Hatta, Mohammad, "Tanggungjawab Kaum Intelegensia", dalam Mohammad Hatta, dkk, *Cendekiawan dan Politik*, Jakarta : Lembaga Penelitian, Pendidikan dan Penerangan Ekonomi dan Sosial LP3ES, 1984.
- Hatta, Mohammad, dkk, *Cendekiawan dan Politik*, Jakarta : Lembaga Penelitian, Pendidikan dan Penerangan Ekonomi dan Sosial LP3ES, 1984.
- Hidayat, Komaruddin, dan Ahmad Gaus AF, "Tipologi Gerakan Islam Kontemporer di Indonesia" dalam Komaruddin Hidayat dan Ahmad Gaus AF (ed.), *Islam Negara & Civil Society Gerakan dan Pemikiran Islam Kontemporer*, Jakarta : Penerbit Oaramadina, 2005.
- Hidayat, Komaruddin, dan Ahmad Gaus AF, (ed.), *Islam Negara & Civil Society Gerakan dan Pemikiran Islam Kontemporer*, Jakarta : Penerbit Oaramadina, 2005.
- Hutchins, Robert Maynard, (ed.), *Great Books of Western World, No. 7, Plato*, Chicago : University of Chicago Press, 1952.
- Imarah, Muhammad, *Perang Terminologi Islam Versus Barat*, Jakarta : Rabbani Press, 1998.
- Jurdi, Syarifuddin, *Pemikiran Politik Islam Indonesia Pertautan Negara, Khilafah, Masyarakat Madani dan Demokrasi*, Yogyakarta : Pustaka Pelajar, 2008.
- Ma'arif, Ahmad Syafi'i, "Format Politik Kita : Sebuah Refleksi", dalam, Th. Sumartana, Elga Sarapung dan Zuly Qodir (Tim Editor), *Reformasi Politik Kebangkitan Agama dan Konsumerisme*, Yogyakarta : Institut DIAN/Interfidei, 2000.
- Madjid, Nurcholish, *Islam Doktrin & Peradaban*, Jakarta : Paramadina dan Dian Rakyat, 2008.
- Madjid, Nurcholish, *Dialog Keterbukaan Artikulasi Nilai Islam dalam Wacana Sosial Politik Kontemporer*, Jakarta : Paramadina, 1998.
- Madjid, Nurcholish, "Cita-Cita Politik Kita", dalam Bosco Carvallo dan Dasrizal, (Penyunting.), *Aspirasi Umat Islam Indonesia*, Jakarta : Lembaga Penunjang Pembangunan Nasional (Leppenpas), 1983.

- Mahendra, Yusril Ihza, *Modernisme dan Fundamentalisme dalam Politik Islam Perbandingan Partai Masyumi Indonesia dan Partai Jama'at Islami Pakistan*, Jakarta : Paramadina, 1999.
- Mulkhan, Abdul Munir, *Paradigma Intelektual Muslim Pengantar Filsafat Pendidikan Islam dan Dakwah*, Yogyakarta : SI Press, 1993.
- Nataatmadja, Hidayat, "Gerakan Islam : Antara Kesemuan, Harapan dan Hakekat", dalam Bosco Carvallo dan Dasrizal, (Penyunting.), *Aspirasi Umat Islam Indonesia*, Jakarta : Lembaga Penunjang Pembangunan Nasional (Leppenas), 1983.
- Pabotinggi, Mochtar, "Pembelaan bagi Nurcholish" dalam, Jalaluddin Rachmat et.al, *Tharikat Nurcholisy Jejak Pemikiran dan Pembaharu Sampai Guru Bangsa*, Yogyakarta : Pustaka Pelajar, 2001.
- Patterson, Charles H., *Cliff's Course Outlines : Western Philosophy Volume I 600 B.C to 1600 A.D*, USA : Cliff's Notre, 1970.
- Pratiknya, Ahmad W., "Anatomi Cendekiawan Muslim Potret Indonesia", dalam, M. Amien Rais (ed.), *Islam Indonesia Suatu Potret Mengaca Diri*, Jakarta : PT RajaGrafindoPersada, 1996.
- Rachman, Budhy Munawar-, *Islam Pluralis Wacana Kesetaraan Kaum Beriman*, Jakarta : Penerbit Paramadina, 2001.
- Rachmat Jalaluddin, et.al, *Tharikat Nurcholisy Jejak Pemikiran dan Pembaharu Sampai Guru Bangsa*, Yogyakarta : Pustaka Pelajar, 2001.
- Rais, M. Amien, "Indonesia dan Demokrasi", dalam Bosco Carvallo dan Dasrizal, (Penyunting.), *Aspirasi Umat Islam Indonesia*, Jakarta : Lembaga Penunjang Pembangunan Nasional (Leppenas), 1983.
- Rais, M. Amien, (ed.), *Islam Indonesia Suatu Potret Mengaca Diri*, Jakarta : PT RajaGrafindoPersada, 1996.
- Sitompul, Agussalim, *Menyatudengan Umat Menyatudengan Bangsa Pemikiran Keislaman Keindonesiaan HMI (1947-1997)*, Jakarta : Logos Wacana Ilmudan Pemikiran, 2002.
- Stoddard, Lothrop, *Dunia Baru Islam*, Jakarta : Penerbitan Negara, 1966.
- Taba, Abdul Aiziz, *Islam dan Negara dalam Politik Orde Baru*, Jakarta : Gema Insani Press, 1996.
- Tobroni dan Syamsul Arifin, *Islam Pluralisme Budaya dan Politik Refleksi Teologi untuk Aksi dalam Keberagamaan dan Pendidikan*, Yogyakarta : SI Press, 1994.

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